

Analysis and Propagation Modeling of Path Loss in THz Spectrum for Indoor Cognitive Scenarios

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Abstract—This paper presents a comparative analysis and propagation modeling of path loss (PL) in terahertz (THz) channels for indoor scenarios at 300 GHz. Experimental measurements in a conference room are used to evaluate several literature-based PL models by comparing their root-mean-square error performance. A custom-developed three-dimensional ray-launching simulation tool is introduced and validated against measurement data, yielding a mean absolute error of 0.77 dB. Furthermore, the study examines the impact of receiver height on PL characteristics by applying the Close-In PL model across multiple vertical levels of the conference room, revealing significant variations in the PL exponent and standard deviation. These findings underscore the need for height-specific channel models to support the design of robust THz communication systems for next-generation networks.

I. INTRODUCTION

Telecommunications have evolved rapidly from 1G to 5G, significantly advancing data rates and connectivity. The 5G networks introduced millimeter wave communication transforming mobile broadband and the Internet of Things [1]. However, the increasing demand for high-speed seamless connectivity has accelerated the development of 6G networks. With expected data rates surpassing one Tbps, 6G aims to interconnect humans, machines, devices, and sensors, thereby fostering applications like tactile internet, smart cities, cognitive environments, industry 5.0, and the Internet of Everything [2].

The terahertz (THz) band (0.1–10 THz), is considered pivotal for 6G networks due to its immense bandwidth, particularly as sub-100 GHz frequencies become congested [3]. However, THz signals experience significant path loss (PL), molecular absorption (e.g., by oxygen and water vapor), and complex propagation, including increased scattering and reduced diffraction [4]. Thus, accurate PL modeling is essential, requiring both deterministic and statistical models. Traditional statistical methods often fail to capture the complexities of THz channels, particularly in challenging environments. Furthermore, THz measurements are hampered by specialized equipment requirements, high costs, and inconsistent material properties, resulting in limited and unreliable data [5].

To address these issues, this study focuses on modeling PL within a typical indoor environment at 300 GHz using a custom-developed, THz three-dimensional Ray-Launching (3D-RL) simulator. The experimental data from a conference room measurement campaign is used to evaluate the precision

of existing THz PL models derived from empirical data collected in specific measurement scenarios and to validate the 3D-RL tool. Height-specific PL modeling under Line-of-Sight (LOS) and Non-Line-of-Sight (NLOS) conditions is then presented to analyze the impact of obstructions and room geometry on THz propagation, aiming to develop robust channel models while mitigating the cost and limitations of traditional measurement methods.

II. ANALYSIS OF RELATED PL MODELING

A review of existing literature highlights various PL models, each designed for specific THz propagation environments. Table I summarizes these models, their measurement scenarios, and methodologies. The root-mean-square error (RMSE) was calculated to evaluate their accuracy by comparing model predictions with empirical data. These data were entirely obtained from the measurement campaign described in [12], which serves as the empirical foundation for this study. This campaign was conducted in an indoor conference room using a time-domain channel sounder operating at 300 GHz with a 2 GHz bandwidth. Measurements were conducted in a 4.7 m × 7.8 m room with a 2.9 m ceiling height, a window facade (north), glass wall (east), and concrete-brick walls (south & west), with a central table, office chairs, a television (south wall), and magnetic boards (west wall). The transmitter (Tx) was placed at 1.86 m height in one corner, directed towards the center, while the rotatable receiver (Rx) was set at 0.93 m on a table. The measurements were taken at eight distinct Rx positions to analyze PL, delay spread, and angular spread. Further technical details on the setup, equipment, and procedure are available in [12].

The study in [6] modeled a 300 GHz channel in a university corridor, examining different scenarios. The 2.3 m-wide, 2.5 m-high corridor had concrete walls, plastic posters, and metal doors. The Tx was mounted 2.35 m high, and the Rx moved from 6 to 45 m in 1 m intervals under LOS. The Close-In (CI) and Floating Intercept (FI) models were used with a reference PL of 82 dB at 1 m. In [7], a vector network analyzer (VNA) based short-range indoor measurements recorded 20 LOS positions from 0.1 m to 2 m. The Tx was fixed, and the Rx moved in 0.1 m increments while data were collected at 12 frequency points between 220 GHz and 330 GHz. The CI, FI, and Alpha-Beta-Gamma (ABG) models were used with a reference PL of 80.52 dB at 0.1 m. The study in [8]

TABLE I: Current PL modeling approaches for THz frequency bands.

Ref.	PL Model	Environment	Freq. (GHz)	Modeling Equation	PL Exponent (n)	Std Dev. (X_σ)
[6]	CI / FI	Indoor / Corridor – Access, Device-to-device (D2D), Backhaul / LoS / 6 - 45m	300	$L_{CI}(d)[\text{dB}] = 10n \log_{10} d + 20 \log_{10} \frac{4\pi f_{\text{GHz}} \times 10^9}{c}$ $\&$ $L_{FI}(d)[\text{dB}] = 10n \log_{10} d + \beta$	Access : spectrum(CI/FI) - MPC(CI/FI) 1.41/1.74 - 1.67/1.58 D2D : spectrum(CI/FI) - MPC(CI/FI) 1.49/1.90 - 1.60/1.66 Backhaul : H-0.12m(CI/FI) - H-0.25m(CI/FI) 1.85/2.01 - 1.68/1.40	CI : 1.35 FI : 1.09
[7]	CI / FI / ABG	Indoor / Optical experimental platform / LoS / 0.1 - 2m	220 - 330	$PL^{CI}(f, d) = FSPL(f, d_0) + 10n \log_{10} \left(\frac{d}{d_0} \right) + X_{\sigma}^{CI}, \quad d > d_0$ $\&$ $PL^{FI}(d) = \alpha + 10n \log_{10}(d) + X_{\sigma}^{FI}$ $\&$ $PL^{ABG}(f, d) = 10n \log_{10} \left(\frac{d}{d_0} \right) + \beta + 10\gamma \log_{10} \left(\frac{f}{1\text{GHz}} \right) + \chi_{\sigma}$	CI : 2.47/2.14/2.21/2.27/2.30/2.20/ 2.32/2.34/2.32/ 1.83 /2.51/2.20 FI : 2.29/2.16/2.36/2.01/2.00/1.82/ 1.80/1.83/1.75/ 1.75 /1.80/1.75 ABG(n) : 1.93 ABG(γ) : 2.10	CI : 2.78 FI : 2.77 ABG : 3.78
[8]	CI / ABG	Indoor / Large hall / LoS/NLoS / 3 - 15.6m	299 - 301	$PL^{CI}(d) [\text{dB}] = 20 \log_{10} \frac{4\pi f c}{c} + 10n \log_{10} d + X_{\sigma_{CI}}$ $\&$ $PL^{ABG}(d) [\text{dB}] = 10n_{ABG} \log_{10} \frac{d}{d_0} + PL_{d_0} + \chi_{\sigma_{ABG}}$	CI : 1.80 ABG : 2.10	–
[9]	CI	Indoor / Lecture room / LoS / 2 - 5m	300 - 310	$PL(d) = \overline{PL}(d_0) + 10n \log_{10} \left(\frac{d}{d_0} \right) + X_{\sigma}, \quad d \geq d_0$	open-open (O-O) : 1.71 horn-horn (H-H) : 1.65 horn-open (H-O) : 1.77	(O-O) : 2.13 (H-H) : 0.46 (H-O) : 0.07
[10]	CI	Indoor / Corridor / LoS / 2.85 - 20m	300	$PL^{CI}(f, d) [\text{dB}] = 10n \log_{10} (d/d_{ref}) + FSPL(f, d_{ref})$ where, $FSPL(f, d_{ref}) [\text{dB}] = -20 \log_{10} \left(\frac{c}{4\pi f d_{ref}} \right)$	omni : 1.40 best : 2.13	–
[11]	CI	Indoor / Corridor / LoS / 5 - 31m	306 - 321	$PL^{CI} [\text{dB}] = 10n \log_{10} (d/d_0) + FSPL(d_0)$ where, $FSPL(f, d_0) = -20 \log_{10} \left(\frac{c}{4\pi f d_0} \right)$	omni : 1.35 best : 1.87	–

characterized 300 GHz channel in a 42 m \times 25 m hall. The measurements spanned 3–15.6 m with a VNA sounder at 8 Rx positions within obstacles like pillars, stairs, and furniture. The CI and ABG models along with a reference PL of 81.98 dB at 1 m was used. Similarly, [9] applied the CI model in a 7.9 m \times 6.5 m lecture room, using different antenna setups. The Rx was positioned at 5 locations over a 70 cm-high wooden table, spaced 1 m apart under LOS conditions. The study in [10] collected 300 GHz channel data in an indoor corridor using an in-house sounder. The 2.38 m \times 20 m corridor had reflective surfaces like metal doors and posters. The Tx was at one end, with 7 LOS Rx locations at 2.85 m intervals. Similarly, [11] conducted 300 GHz measurements in a glass-walled corridor with metal pillars and wooden doors, applying the CI model. The Tx and Rx were at 2.5 m and 2 m heights, with 21 Rx positions: 15 from 5–19 m and 6 from 21–31 m with 1 m and 2 m intervals respectively.

Figure 1 compares models from these studies with data collected in a conference room. RMSE values for each fitting curve are indicated in the legend, with interpolated curves matched to measurement distances. The x-axis is truncated at 5.5 m for visibility, though actual measurements extend to 45 m. The CI model consistently showed lower RMSE values than FI and ABG, though the lowest RMSE (7.73 dB) still indicates a significant error margin, potentially limiting

practical applications.

III. 3D-RL SIMULATION AND PL ANALYSIS

A. RL Validation

To enhance the understanding of THz propagation and address measurement limitations, this section presents a 3D-RL deterministic simulator. It employs geometrical optics and the uniform theory of diffraction to model ray transmission in a 3D environment. The rays are emitted based on angular distributions to mimic antenna patterns, with trajectories tracked in a 3D matrix. The RL algorithm accounts for reflections, refractions, and diffractions, modifying ray paths until they exit the area or reach a reflection limit. The algorithm's modular design supports multi-frequency analysis using electromagnetic material data libraries. A THz-specific material property library with empirically measured data [13], has been incorporated into the simulator along with key electromagnetic effects, including surface reflections, refractions, diffractions, scattering, and atmospheric attenuation enabling precise site-specific modeling.

To validate the tool's accuracy, simulation results were compared with measured data from the conference room, assessing PL at eight locations. Figure 2 shows the simulated and measured results, with a mean absolute error of 0.77

Fig. 1: RMSE comparison of PL models from the literature.

Fig. 2: Validation of 3D-RL tool with measured PL.

dB, indicating strong correlation and the tool's reliability in volumetric THz propagation analysis.

B. PL Modeling

This section presents the modeling and analysis of PL using the CI model, which effectively characterizes signal attenuation at a given frequency [6]–[11]. The CI model is mathematically expressed as:

$$PL(f, d) = FSPL(f, d_0) + 10n \log_{10} \left(\frac{d}{d_0} \right) + X_\sigma \quad (1)$$

where $PL(f, d)$ denotes the PL in decibels (dB) at a distance d , n represents the PLE, and d_0 is the reference distance, set to 1 meter in this study. The term X_σ accounts for shadow fading, following a Gaussian distribution with zero mean and standard deviation (SD) σ in dB. The free-space path loss (FSPL) is derived from Friis' transmission equation:

$$FSPL(f, d_0) = 20 \log_{10} \left(\frac{4\pi f d_0}{c} \right) \quad (2)$$

where f is 300 GHz, and c is the speed of light. The CI model's key parameter, n , is estimated using the minimum mean square error technique for optimal fit while minimizing errors.

For PL modeling, the THz 3D-RL simulation tool was utilized, incorporating the full volumetric data obtained from simulating the validated conference room environment. The room was discretized into 26 height levels, with data classified as LOS or NLOS based on a centrally placed table at height 9. Heights above 10 were categorized as LOS, while lower heights were considered NLOS. The CI model was applied to each height level, and corresponding parameters n and X_σ were computed, as summarized in Table II.

The analysis of Table II reveals a clear trend in the variation of the PLE (n), SD (X_σ) and, the number of data points across different heights in both NLOS and LOS scenarios. At lower heights (1–9), n is relatively high (4.92–3.62), indicating significant signal attenuation due to NLOS conditions. The highest n (4.92) is observed at height 1, suggesting stronger propagation losses closer to the ground with increased obstructions and reflections. The number of data points varies across different heights in NLOS case, with the highest count at height 6 and the lowest at height 7. This variation in data density is attributed to obstructions affecting signal reception. A notable outlier is observed at height 9, where n increases to 4.52 with the highest SD of 20.89, possibly due to interference effects caused by the table at the same height.

In contrast, as height increases beyond 10, a sharp decline in n is evident, stabilizing around 2.47 at height 26. This reduction in n signifies improved propagation conditions, due to fewer obstacles and the dominance of LOS. The number of data points in the LOS region remains consistently high at 2970 & 3175, ensuring statistical reliability in the derived PLE and SD values. Similarly, the SD follows a decreasing trend as the height increases, indicating more stable propagation

TABLE II: Comparison of parameters for different heights.

Height	Scenario	Data Points	PLE (n) (95% confidence bound)	Std Dev. (X_σ)
1	NLOS	2878	4.92 (4.83, 5.00)	15.45
2	NLOS	2880	4.65 (4.57, 4.73)	14.54
3	NLOS	2552	4.58 (4.49, 4.67)	14.58
4	NLOS	2552	4.52 (4.42, 4.61)	15.02
5	NLOS	2931	4.49 (4.40, 4.57)	14.72
6	NLOS	2932	4.26 (4.18, 4.34)	14.24
7	NLOS	1895	3.87 (3.77, 3.98)	15.21
8	NLOS	1895	3.62 (3.53, 3.71)	13.14
9	NLOS	2679	4.52 (4.40, 4.65)	20.89
10	LOS	2970	2.82 (2.77, 2.87)	9.58
11	LOS	2970	2.71 (2.66, 2.76)	9.54
12	LOS	3175	2.63 (2.58, 2.68)	9.81
13	LOS	3175	2.60 (2.55, 2.65)	8.82
14	LOS	3175	2.64 (2.59, 2.68)	8.95
15	LOS	3175	2.62 (2.57, 2.67)	8.91
16	LOS	3175	2.66 (2.61, 2.71)	9.06
17	LOS	3175	2.75 (2.70, 2.81)	10.27
18	LOS	3175	2.69 (2.64, 2.74)	9.41
19	LOS	3175	2.66 (2.61, 2.70)	8.39
20	LOS	3175	2.71 (2.66, 2.75)	8.91
21	LOS	3175	2.65 (2.61, 2.70)	9.06
22	LOS	3175	2.61 (2.56, 2.66)	9.27
23	LOS	3175	2.64 (2.59, 2.70)	9.82
24	LOS	3175	2.56 (2.51, 2.61)	9.38
25	LOS	3175	2.53 (2.48, 2.58)	9.57
26	LOS	3175	2.47 (2.42, 2.52)	9.77

conditions at elevated positions.

A closer look at the data for height 10, just above the table, is illustrated in Figure 3. The 3D-RL data points show a moderate spread around the fitting curve, reflecting the balance between LOS and scattering paths for this height. The PL generally increases with distance, consistent with theoretical expectations while moderate SD suggests relatively stable propagation compared to lower heights. These findings underscore the impact of obstructions and room geometry on THz wave propagation, emphasizing the need for height-specific modeling for accurate PL characterization.

Fig. 3: Modeling of PL using 3D-RL tool for 10th height.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, this work has advanced the understanding of indoor THz propagation by combining empirical measurements with a detailed 3D-RL simulation approach. The comparative analysis of established PL models demonstrated that the CI model consistently yields lower RMSE values compared to FI and ABG models, though with considerable errors that highlight the challenges of modeling at 300 GHz. The investigation into height-dependent behavior revealed marked variations in the PLE, emphasizing the influence of environmental obstructions and room geometry on THz signal attenuation. These insights advocate for the development of customized, height-specific channel models to better predict propagation conditions in indoor scenarios.

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